

THE ROLE OF GROUP-BASED MENTAL HEALTH PROGRAMME IN PROMOTING EMOTIONAL WELL- BEING AND CONNECTION AMONG STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the role of a group-based mental health programme in promoting emotional well-being and social connection among university students. We examined the experiences of eight female undergraduate students who participated in a one-month group-based mental health programme using a qualitative design. Participants reported feeling less isolated, more emotionally aware, and more confident in managing personal and interpersonal challenges. The group-based intervention appeared to promote emotional well-being in the context of higher education by fostering emotional validation, shared understanding, and a supportive environment.

Introduction

Most university students face academic pressure, uncertainty about future careers, and limited access to psychological support while pursuing higher education. It has been consistently demonstrated that elevated levels of stress, anxiety, and emotional distress are common among students, particularly among freshmen during the transition to university life, when academic demands intensify and social environments change rapidly (Auerbach et al., 2016; Bantjes et al., 2022; Ramsay et al., 2007). They appear especially vulnerable during this period, often reporting difficulties in adaptation, feelings of isolation, and underdeveloped academic and self-regulation skills (Mohammadyari, 2012; Mofatteh, 2021).

Despite an increasing number of mental health concerns among students, access to psychological support still remains limited. Even if there is high demand, many students do not seek or receive professional help, often due to stigma, uncertainty about the severity of their problems, or the perception that available services are inaccessible or only intended for crisis situations (Corrigan & Rüscher, 2002; Russell et al., 2008; WHO, 2022). Especially low- and middle-income countries fall into this category, as counselling services remain privatized, or financially inaccessible, leaving preventive and developmental needs insufficiently addressed (Hyseni Duraku et al., 2024).

In parallel with these challenges, students frequently report academic stress linked to poor time management, ineffective study strategies, and perfectionistic cognitive patterns, which may contribute to emotional exhaustion and reduced academic functioning (Hu et al., 2023; Obando Posada et al., 2023). All these are further compounded by career uncertainty, as many students feel unprepared to make serious decisions about their professional future or

lack access to guidance and mentorship (Salim et al., 2023). Overall, the need for support approaches should be highlighted to address students' emotional, academic, and developmental experiences in an integrated manner within the context of higher education.

When addressing key factors that support students' well-being and academic engagement, social support must be mentioned as a key protective factor, particularly during periods of transition (Chang et al., 2020). Research has found that strong sense of belonging within the university environment is associated with greater motivation, persistence, and academic success (Axelson & Flick, 2010; Kuh, 2003). However, many students struggle to form meaningful social connections due to large class sizes, limited structured peer interaction, and socioeconomic or identity-related barriers to engagement (Eames & Stewart, 2008).

To solve this problem, peer-based and mutual support groups have emerged as a promising strategy to foster connection and psychological well-being among students. They bring together individuals with shared experiences or challenges to exchange emotional, informational, and practical support within a reciprocal and non-hierarchical structure (Mead et al., 2001; Steinberg, 2014). Originally developed in healthcare settings, such groups are increasingly implemented in educational contexts, where they provide spaces for shared reflection, emotional validation, and collaborative problem-solving (Darby Penney, 2018; Crisp et al., 2020).

Evidence suggests that participation in peer or mutual support groups is associated with reduced emotional distress, improved coping, and enhanced self-efficacy (Byrom, 2017; Pointon-Haas et al., 2024). Because group-based formats combine emotional safety with practical skill-sharing, allowing participants to learn adaptive strategies while simultaneously experiencing social connection, they can be particularly effective for students. Salim et al. (2023) have found that the most important benefits appear to extend beyond emotional well-being, influencing academic confidence, career clarity, and attitudes toward psychological support.

Another theoretical framework that helps explain these outcomes is the concept of sense of community introduced by McMillan and Chavis (1986), who define it as a feeling of belonging, mutual mattering, and shared faith that members' needs will be met through commitment to the group. Their model identifies four key components: membership, influence, fulfillment of needs, and shared emotional connection. Moreover, positive associations between sense of community and psychological well-being, life satisfaction, and meaning in life, as well as negative associations with loneliness, stress, depression, and self-criticism have been demonstrated by research across diverse populations (Herrero et al., 2011; Michalski et al., 2020; Prezza et al., 2005).

Additionally, group interventions grounded in cognitive-behavioral principles have also shown effectiveness in improving students' emotional regulation, reducing anxiety, and addressing maladaptive thought patterns related to academic pressure (Beck et al., 1979; Beck, 2020). Especially when combined with social support processes, group-based CBT-oriented interventions appear to produce synergistic effects by offering practical coping tools

(Worsley et al., 2022). Such integration may be highly valuable in contexts where formal mental health services are limited.

Despite growing interest in peer and group-based interventions, systematic reviews highlight the need for further context-specific and practice-based research, especially in the context of middle or low-income settings as there is limited qualitative research exploring how students themselves experience group-based self-development programmes (Byrom, 2017).

The present study addresses this gap by exploring the experiences of female university students who participated in a one-month group-based mental health programme. For examining how participants perceived the impact of the programme on their emotional well-being, sense of belonging, self-confidence, and attitudes toward psychological support, a qualitative approach will be used. By focusing on students' own reflections, this study aims to contribute practice-based insight into the role of group interventions as accessible and meaningful support tools within higher education.

Method

Participants

This study was conducted at the Uzbekistan State World Languages University and included eight female undergraduate students ($M_{age} = 19.75$, $SD = 2.49$) who voluntarily enrolled in a group-based self-development and mental health programme. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to the start of the programme.

Participants' characteristics along with their initial motivations for participation are represented in Table 1.

Participant	Age	Gender	Field of Study	Year of Study	Initial Motivation for Participation
1	18	Female	English and Literature	1	Self-development
2	19	Female	English Philology	2	Self-development, psychological growth
3	18	Female	English and Literature	1	Difficulties in adjustment to university life, peer-related difficulties
4	19	Female	English Philology	2	Self-development, psychological growth

5	25	Female	English Philology	2	Self- development, psychological growth
6	19	Female	English Philology	2	Interest in mentorship support, psychological growth
7	18	Female	English and Literature	1	Difficulties in adjustment to university life, psychological growth
8	22	Female	Russian Philology	4	Self-doubt, reduced motivation, blame, social isolation

Design

A qualitative design was employed to explore participants' experiences following a one-month group-based self-development and mental health programme. Data were collected using an anonymous online questionnaire administered via Google Forms to ensure confidentiality and ethical protection of participants' privacy.

The questionnaire included one item assessed on a 10-point Likert scale to evaluate participants' perceptions of how well the programme met its intended outcomes. In addition, open-ended questions explored perceived gains from the programme, challenges encountered, and suggestions for future improvement. Participants were able to respond in their preferred language, either Uzbek or Russian.

Data Analysis

To ensure a systematic approach to data analysis, a thematic analysis was conducted based on participants' responses to the open-ended survey questions. All the answers were developed into four themes in relation to the impact of the programme and experience of participants in the mental health programme: (1) sense of belonging and group connection, (2) emotional awareness and validation, (3) growth in self-confidence, and (4) perceived improvement in emotional well-being.

Results

The findings presented below are based on participants' written reflections collected upon completion of the one-month group-based self-development programme. The results are organized into four thematic domains that reflect participants' perspectives on their

experiences, the changes they reported, and their perceptions of how the group context contributed to these outcomes. To preserve anonymity and ensure ethical sensitivity of students, the findings are reported in a summarized and paraphrased form.

1. Sense of Belonging and Group Connection

By the end of the programme, most students reported the emergence of a strong sense of belonging and group connection. Participants described the group environment as open, supportive, and non-judgmental, which allowed them to speak freely and engage in honest discussions. The opportunity to share personal experiences within the group helped participants feel understood and less alone in their struggles.

Two students who reported peer-related difficulties in the beginning, described how hearing others articulate similar concerns appeared to normalize their experiences and reduce feelings of isolation. One participant who had previously experienced emotional withdrawal and apathy reported that seeing others as “human like herself” contributed to emotional relief and renewed engagement. Group discussions were described as collaborative due to active supporting atmosphere among participants. This collective problem-solving process strengthened feelings of community and mutual care.

2. Emotional Awareness and Validation

Another reports from most of the students were regarding noticeable psychological changes, particularly in relation to emotional awareness and self-reflection. Participants described becoming more attentive to their thoughts, emotions, and behavioral patterns following participation in the programme. Moreover, several students noted that they began to question their reactions more consciously before acting.

Besides that, participants frequently reported letting go of negative or unhelpful thought patterns, which they associated with improvements in mood and outlook on life. This process of cognitive and emotional reflection appeared to help participants reinterpret daily experiences more positively and develop a greater sense of internal balance. Some participants described this change as a form of self-discovery, reporting that they felt they had “rediscovered” themselves and gained a clearer understanding of their inner experiences.

3. Growth in Self-Confidence

The next benefit of the group-based mental health programme which was also reported by participants` experiences was increased self-confidence. Several reflections indicated a shift from externalizing blame toward greater sense of personal responsibility. Participants described becoming more aware of their own role in interpersonal situations and feeling better equipped to adapt to challenges rather than feeling overwhelmed by them.

These changes were perceived as contributing to positive developments not only within the participants themselves but also in their relationships with others, including family and friends.

4. Perceived Improvement in Emotional Well-being

Finally, another improvements frequently reported were in perceived emotional well-being. Participants described feeling emotionally lighter, calmer, and more hopeful both after every session and prior to completing the programme. In addition, some participants noted that the group experience also helped them find a sense of meaning and joy in their lives, particularly during periods when they had previously felt disengaged or emotionally flat.

In addition to qualitative responses, participants evaluated the extent to which the programme met its intended outcomes using a 10-point Likert scale. Overall, the programme was rated highly valuable by most participants. No participants reported low ratings, indicating general satisfaction with the programme's outcomes.

Results are presented in the diagram below.

Diagram 1. Responses to the question "On a scale from 1 to 10, how beneficial was the programme for you overall": 65% rated the programme as 10; 25% - as 9; and 12.5% - as 8.

Discussion

The present study explored how female university students experienced a short-term group-based mental health programme, with particular attention to emotional well-being, sense of belonging, self-confidence, and attitudes toward psychological support. Overall, participants' reflections suggest that the programme was experienced as meaningful, supportive, and personally relevant, with the group format itself playing a central role in shaping these outcomes.

Sense of Belonging and Group Connection

One of the most prominent findings of this study was the strong sense of belonging and connection reported by participants. Students often described the group as a place where they felt accepted and understood. Feeling less alone was a recurring point across reflections. This experience aligns closely with the concept of sense of community as described by McMillan and Chavis (1986), which emphasizes belonging, mutual support, and shared emotional connection as key components of supportive group environments.

It should also be noted that previous research has shown that a strong sense of community is associated with greater psychological well-being, life satisfaction, and meaning in life, as well as lower levels of loneliness, stress, and depressive symptoms (Herrero et al., 2011; Michalski et al., 2020). In this study, being among peers with similar experiences appeared to normalize students' difficulties and reduce emotional isolation, particularly for those who initially reported peer-related challenges or emotional withdrawal.

Furthermore, for some students, the experience of belonging appeared to be new rather than familiar, which may explain why it was described so strongly in their reflections. This suggests that group-based interventions may be particularly valuable for students who struggle to find connection within more formal or impersonal university settings especially for those who reside away from their families.

Emotional Awareness and Validation

Participants also reported noticeable changes in emotional awareness and self-reflection. Rather than describing dramatic transformations, students spoke about gradual shifts, such as noticing their thoughts more clearly or pausing before reacting. This might be a result of cognitive-behavioural approaches, where attention is mostly directed toward thoughts, emotions, and behavioral responses (Beck et al., 1979; Beck, 2020).

Importantly, emotional awareness in this study was closely linked to emotional validation within the group. Hearing others articulate similar feelings appeared to reduce self-criticism and promote acceptance. Studies have continuously highlighted that social support that fosters validation and empathetic understanding are key emotional resources that help overcome stress and strengthen psychological resilience (Foa & Foa, 1980; Helgeson & Gottlieb, 2000).

This study also has shown that even brief group-based interventions may support emotional regulation through relational processes.

Growth in Self-Confidence and Personal Responsibility

Another key outcome reported by participants was increased self-confidence and a stronger sense of personal responsibility. Students described becoming more aware of their own role in interpersonal situations and feeling more capable of adapting to challenges. This shift away from externalizing blame toward self-reflection suggests a growing sense of agency, rather than a sudden or complete change in confidence.

These findings are consistent with research indicating that group interventions can enhance self-efficacy by combining emotional support with opportunities for shared problem-solving and modelling (Toseland & Rivas, 2014; Worsley et al., 2022). In the present study, increased confidence appeared to extend beyond the group context, influencing participants' relationships with family members and friends. This suggests that changes experienced within the group may generalize to broader areas of students' lives, even within a relatively short intervention period.

Perceived Emotional Well-Being and Meaning

Last but not least, participants frequently described improvements in emotional well-being, including feeling calmer, emotionally lighter, and more hopeful. For some students, the

programme also appeared to support a renewed sense of meaning and engagement with life, particularly during periods previously marked by apathy or emotional flatness.

Moreover, feeling seen, heard, and supported by others seemed to restore motivation and emotional engagement especially in academic lives of students.

The findings of this study point to the value of short-term, group-based self-development programmes as accessible and meaningful supplements to existing student support services, particularly in settings where counselling services are limited, costly, or underutilized.

For university psychologists, these findings highlight the importance of creating psychologically safe group environments that prioritize openness, mutual respect, and shared reflection. Even brief interventions may have meaningful impact when students feel connected and validated within the group.

This study has several limitations. Firstly, these findings cannot be generalized for all contexts due to the small sample size and focus on female students. In addition, data were based on self-reported reflections collected at the end of the programme, which may be influenced by social desirability or recall bias.

Future research could examine similar programmes with more diverse samples, longer follow-up periods, and mixed-method designs. Further exploration of how sense of community develops over time within student groups may deepen understanding of the mechanisms underlying emotional and psychological change..

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